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Research Article

**EVALUATE THE CAUSES OF STRESS AMONG NURSES
WORKING IN IN CRITICAL AREA AT ALLAMA IQBAL
MEMORIAL TEACHING HOSPITAL SIALKOT**¹Shazia Asghar, ²Shaidha Parveen, ³Zainab Suleman¹Charge Nurse, DHQ Muzaffargarh, Pakistan²Charge Nurse, DHQ Muzaffargarh, Pakistan³Principal, College Of Nursing, Khawaja Muhamamd Safdar Medical College, Sialkot, Pakistan**Abstract:**

Background: Nursing is widely known as a stressful profession but intensive care unit is the most stressful; when nurses fail to cope with workplace, stresses' complications such as burnout and depression ensue, and this can compromise the quality of nursing care.

Objective: To evaluate causes of stress among nurses working in intensive care unit of a public sector hospital, Sialkot.

Methodology: This is descriptive exploratory study conducted for the period of 6 weeks in which participants were recruited via random sampling technique. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data from study participants.

Results: Total 15 study participants having age range 20 years to 60 years recruited for this research work. To sum up causes of stress among 15 ICU nurses, 26.67% (n=4) respondents said lack of knowledge about operating special equipment; 20% (n=3) said excess workload; 13.33% (n=2) shortage of staff, prolonged shifts and lack of cooperation among nurses whereas 6.67% (n=1) said improper communication between doctors and nurses and lack of resources and availability of equipment (Ventilators etc.) were the prime causes of stress they had to face during working in their respective ICUs.

Conclusion: Hence, it can be concluded from current study result findings that nurses working in Intensive Care Units are facing numerous sources of stress and prime causes were lack of knowledge about operating special equipment, excess workload, shortage of staff, prolonged shifts, lack of cooperation among nurses, improper communication between doctors and nurses and also lack of resources and availability of equipment (ventilators, etc).

Keywords: Stress; Intensive Care Unit; Nurses; Causes; Sources

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INTRODUCTION:

Intensive care nurses were consistently exposed to a wide range of stresses. Their responsibilities include giving advanced treatment to severely ill patients while handling numerous work-related hurdles.¹ Stress is a widespread psychological phenomena especially among critical care nurses. The intensive care unit (ICU) is a demanding setting because nurses must cope with heavy workloads and high-acuity patients, provide advanced nursing care and use advanced technology. As a result, nurses experience enormous everyday pressures, which can have a negative impact on nursing and patient care. As a result, ICU nurses may offer poor quality treatment while also experiencing job discontent and burnout.²

As a result, excessive stress levels among ICU nurses can have detrimental repercussions such as occupational burnout, an increased risk of depression, and poor quality nursing care.³ A recent study found that critical care nurses have an average stress score of 17.71, with 11.7%, 87%, and 1.3% suffering low, moderate, or severe stress, respectively.⁴ Another study indicated that around 1057 (28%) participants had moderate to severe stress levels.⁵ Stress is the degree to which a person regards life conditions as overwhelming, unexpected, and unmanageable.⁶

Research indicates that around 71% of intensive care nurses experience significant levels of stress.⁷ In a sample of 50 critical care nurses, 90% reported experiencing physical and psychological stress.⁸ Research has identified many strains for intensive care nurses, including fear of patient death, intubation, and witnessing patient pain, as well as issues such as low levels of collaboration, negative relationships with supervisors, and high nurse-to-patient ratios.⁹ Meanwhile, discrimination, criticism, disagreements with superiors, and job discontent with pay and workload all contributed to increased stress among ICU nurses.¹⁰

Research into the causes of stress among ICU nurses is currently restricted in underdeveloped countries, highlighting the crucial need for more inquiry. The ICU environment, widely recognized for its high stress levels, presents substantial problems for both nurses and patients. Nurses in these environments frequently face stresses that might harm their physical and emotional health. Without recognizing the sources of stress among ICU nurses, it will be impossible to develop effective coping mechanisms to reduce stress levels, which can be debilitating. However, the biggest gaps in determining the causes of stress among ICU nurses are a lack of standardized stress assessment tools and a scarcity of extensive

research concentrating on specific aspects of ICU job that contribute to stress. Research should also take into account ICU nurses' different origins and experiences, as well as their cultural, economic, and educational contexts. Hence, this study is undertaken in a public sector hospital, Sialkot to determine the causes of stress among ICU nurses.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Research design: Descriptive exploratory.

Research method: Quantitative

Target population: Nurses working in different intensive care units of a public sector hospital, Sialkot.

Sample size: Solvan's formulae used to find sample size as under:

If $N = \text{Population} = 16$

$n = \text{Sample size,}$

$E = \text{Margin of error} = 0.05$

$n = N / 1 + (N) (E)^2$

$n = 16 / 1 + (16) (0.05)^2$

$n = 16 / 1 + (16) (0.0025)$

$n = 16 / 1 + 0.04$

$n = 16 / 1.04 = 15.38$

Hence, required sample size is 15.

Sampling technique: Random sampling technique

Sample selection: Participants recruited/excluded on behalf of listed below criteria:

a) Inclusion criteria:

- Only those nurses who were permanently working in intensive care units.
- Nurses with age range 20 years to 60 years participated in the study.
- All the eligible nurses working ICU, CCU, NICU, PICU, MICU & Emergency ward.

b) Exclusion criteria:

- Nurses working in other departments other than ICU.
- Nurses less than 20 years age.
- Nurses whose working experience in ICU was less than 1 year.
- Nursing students or students on rotation.

Research tool: A well-structured questionnaire contained of close-ended questions.

Data collection procedure: This study was conducted for the period of 6 weeks (From 1st April, 2025 to 15th May, 2025). After approval from IRB, researcher initiated the research by visiting the respective public sector hospital and obtained approval from concerned HODs by explaining the purpose of the study. The Interviewee was selected

on a random sampling basis. The research was carried out through a survey method for data collection. A highly organized and well-designed questionnaire format was utilized to get clear data on the Interviewee's concepts and attitudes. The informants were wanted to know and scaled on a 'Likert Scale' was used to assess causes of stress among study participants.

Ethical consideration: The researcher informed to the participants (orally and in written form) about the aim of this study in terms of their participation with the help of a full consent form and this was achieved via a letter attached to the questionnaire. Written consent was taken from each respondent. Privacy, confidentiality and anonymity was assured and maintained.

Data analysis: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 27) was used to record data in which it was presented in frequencies, percentages and graphs.

RESULTS:

This is descriptive exploratory study undertaken at a public sector hospital, Sialkot in which total 15 study participants recruited. There were 13.33% (n=2) participants between age range (20-25) years; 26.67% (n=4) were from (26-30) years; 20% (n=3) respondents having age (31-35) years; 26.67% (n=4) participants between age range (36-40) years and remaining 13.33% (n=2) participants were ≥ 41 years. There were 40% (n=6) married and 60% (n=9) unmarried respondents appeared in the study as displayed in table 1 & figure 1-2.

Now, as per experience in respective ICUs, 40% (n=6) having 1 to 5 years; 26.67% (n=4) with 6 to 10 years and rest of 33.33% (n=5) with an experience >10 years. Regarding concerned ICU, 6.67% (n=1) participant was from MICU; 20% (n=3) from SICU; 26.67% (n=4) from PICU; 13.33% (n=2) were working in NICU while others 33.33% (n=5) working in CICU as presented in table 1 & figure 4-5.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of study participants

Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
20-25 years	2	13.33
26-30 years	4	26.67
31-35 years	3	20.00
36-40 years	4	26.67
≥ 41 years	2	13.33
Total	15	100.00
Marital status		
Married	6	40.00
Unmarried	9	60.00
Total	15	100.00
Qualification		
Diploma nurse	3	20.00
BSN	10	66.67
Master	2	13.33
Total	15	100.00
Position		
Staff nurse	7	46.67
Supervisor nurse	6	40.00
Head nurse	2	13.33
Total	15	100.00
Years worked as a nurse		
1-3 years	2	13.33
4-6 years	4	26.67
7-9 years	6	40.00
10 & above years	3	20.00
Total	15	100.00

Years worked in critical area		
1-5 years	6	40.00
6-10 years	4	26.67
>10 years	5	33.33
Total	15	100.00
Working ICU		
MICU	1	6.67
SICU	3	20.00
PICU	4	26.67
NICU	2	13.33
CICU	5	33.33
Total	15	100.00

Figure 1: Age distribution of study participants

Figure 2: Marital status of study participants

Figure 3: Working experience of study participants in ICU

Figure 4: Working ICU of study respondents

Regarding causes of stress among nurses working in ICU, in the sample of 15 nurses, 80% respondents said that lack of knowledge about operating special equipment i.e. (ventilators, etc.) was main cause of stress in ICU while 20% disagreed with the statement. As well as 73.33% nurses reported that lack of practice and inadequate skills in performing

any procedure as well as excess workload was also causes of stress among them whereas 26.67% disagreed as representing in table 2.

Similarly, 66.67% study participants said that shortage of nursing staff in ICU was also a source of stress while 33.33% was not agree with this statement. Whereas 73.33% study participants said

that prolonged duties and extra shifts was also a major source of stress among ICU nurses and rest of study participants disagreed. On the other side, 86.67% study participants disclosed that lack of cooperation among nurses was also a source of stress while remaining 13.33% disagreed as shown in table 2.

In addition, 86.67% nurses said that lack of resources & availability of equipment (Ventilator etc.) as well as inappropriate communication between nurses and doctors were causes of stress among nurses working in ICUs and rest of 13.33% respondents were

disagreed. To sum up causes of stress among 15 ICU nurses, 26.67% (n=4) respondents said lack of knowledge about operating special equipment; 20% (n=3) said excess workload; 13.33% (n=2) shortage of staff, prolonged shifts and lack of cooperation among nurses whereas 6.67% (n=1) said improper communication between doctors and nurses and lack of resources and availability of equipment (Ventilators etc.) were the prime causes of stress they had to face during working in their respective ICUs as recorded in table 2 & figure 5.

Table 2: Causes of stress among study participants in respective ICUs

Sr. no.	Description	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Lack of knowledge about operating special equipment i.e. (ventilators, etc.) can cause stress.	9 (60%)	3 (20%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)
2	Lack of practice and inadequate skills in performing Any procedure can cause stress. (ABGS sampling, etc.).	4 (26.67%)	7 (46.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (13.33%)	2 (13.33%)
3	The excess workload is a reason for stress.	3 (20%)	8 (53.33%)	1 (6.67%)	2 (13.33%)	1 (6.67%)
4	Shortage of staff is a source of stress.	6 (40%)	4 (26.67%)	2 (13.33%)	2 (13.33%)	1 (6.67%)
5	Prolonged shifts or extra duties (night duty and overtime) are the sources of stress.	2 (13.33%)	9 (60%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)	2 (13.33%)
6	Lack of motivation and recognition for one's effort is a reason for stress.	6 (40%)	2 (13.33%)	1 (6.67%)	2 (13.33%)	4 (26.67%)
7	Prolong standing and no time for a break is a reason for Stress.	8 (53.33%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)	3 (20%)	2 (13.33%)
8	Lack of support from the supervisor/manager is a source of stress.	4 (26.67%)	3 (20%)	2 (13.33%)	4 (26.67%)	2 (13.33%)
9	Conflict with doctors during duty hours can cause stress.	4 (26.67%)	8 (53.33%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)
10	Lack of cooperation among nurses is a cause of stress.	11 (73.33%)	2 (13.33%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)
11	Lack of resources and availability of equipment can(ventilators, etc) cause Stress.	7 (46.67%)	6 (40%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)
12	The unexpected death of the patient is a cause of stress.	7 (46.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (13.33%)	4 (26.67%)	2 (13.33%)
13	Problematic or bad-mannered behavior of patients is the reason for stress.	5 (33.33%)	2 (13.33%)	1 (6.67%)	3 (20%)	4 (26.67%)
14	Aggressive and demanding family members are the source of stress.	3 (20%)	2 (13.33%)	2 (13.33%)	4 (26.67%)	4 (26.67%)

15	The patient is undergoing a painful procedure (CVP line, CPR, etc) is a reason for stress.	2 (13.33%)	5 (33.33%)	1 (6.67%)	4 (26.67%)	3
16	Possibility or fear of getting cross-infection from patient scan (tuberculosis, hepatitis B, C) causes stress.	3 (20%)	2 (13.33%)	2 (13.33%)	4 (26.67%)	4 (26.67%)
17	An improper work environment (noisy surroundings etc) is an origin of stress.	4 (26.67%)	2 (13.33%)	1 (6.67%)	3 (20%)	5 (33.33%)
18	Inappropriate communication between nurses and doctors can cause stress.	12 (80%)	1 (6.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.67%)	1 (6.67%)

Figure 5: Major causes of stress among ICU nurses

DISCUSSION:

Current study depicted that nurses working in ICUs are suffering from multiple sources of stress deteriorating their mental and physical health and causing poor quality of life (QoL). This study result is similar to the findings of Salma Johan et al., who found the major causes of stress among ICU nurses were inappropriate or poor communication between doctors and nurses, lack of support and motivation, unexpected deaths or patients undergoing painful procedures, lack of breaks, lack of cooperation from

peers and supervisors/managers. The patients themselves can also be a source of stress for example, problematic patients or their aggressive family members as well as improper work environment also contributed to stress.¹¹

Meanwhile, a study conducted by Shila Latifzadeh in Ahwaz, Iran, is also consistent with current result findings as ICUs nurses also suffered from stress due to prolonged shifts and prolonged duties without breaks.¹² Moreover, Khan *et al.*, also reported that

ICU nurses suffered from stress due to work overload is in accordance with this study result.¹³ Similarly, current study also showed same result as Pawar who stated that nurses working in ICU suffer from severe stress due to lack of support from supervisors and manager.¹⁴

Additionally, Mosadeghrad also determined that nurses working in ICU suffered from stress due to poor communication between nurses and doctors which is comparative to current study result.¹⁵ As well as, this study result are in line with Mehta & Singh who found that lack of proper communication amongst nurses was also as source of stress in 68% of ICU nurses while 64% nurses reported stress was caused due when they were facing problems with peers and nurses.¹⁶

Moreover, Munyanziza et al., findings are also showed same result as this study that main causes of stress among ICU nurses were care for suffering/dying, or agitated patients and heavy workload.¹⁷ Furthermore, Inoue KC, Ristin et al., discovered that fear of making mistakes in highly technological and complicated nursing care for the critically ill patients seem to be the source of stress in the Intensive Care Unit is also comparative to this study.¹⁸

Likewise, a study done by Johan et al., in Pakistan has similar findings as current study that ICU nurses strongly agreed that excessive workload was the main cause of workplace stress.¹⁹ In addition, the same study done in Saudi Arabia by Alharbi H, Alshehry A. found that nursing participants strongly agreed that aggressive and demanding family members of patients were a greater source of workplace stress in ICU.²⁰ In a nutshell, it can be concluded that nurses working in the ICU are working under highly stressful working conditions.

CONCLUSION:

Hence, it can be concluded from current study result findings that nurses working in Intensive Care Units are facing numerous sources of stress and prime causes were lack of knowledge about operating special equipment, excess workload, shortage of staff, prolonged shifts, lack of cooperation among nurses, improper communication between doctors and nurses and also lack of resources and availability of equipment (ventilators, etc). Although head nurses having good stress management techniques as compared to younger nurses necessitating to initiate some stress management techniques to junior nurses to cope up with stressful events in respective ICUs.

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